

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

PROCESSES MAP

[SMART WEST]

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE 6

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – M4C2 1.5 of PNRR funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU (Grant agreement no. ECS00000036).

1. Introduction

Remote work (RW) and hybrid work have significantly transformed the functioning of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Italy, particularly during the pandemic. The health crisis accelerated the digitalisation of business processes and pushed many companies to reconsider their organisational models, including remote work. However, SMEs approached this transition differently, with varying outcomes depending on the sector, company size, and organisational culture. The "SMART WEST" project provides an in-depth study of the organisational and social transformations that RW has brought about. Specifically, this report examines how SMEs in North-West Italy, selected for this research, implemented remote work during the pandemic and adapted their work and communication processes in the post-pandemic phase. It explores communication flows, the digital tools used, and the changes in organisational and social dynamics within these firms. The objective is to map the organisational and social processes, the information and communication flows, and the digital tools employed, with a specific focus on SMEs and groups of micro and small enterprises. This allows for a better understanding of how RW has reshaped working practices and business management in contexts traditionally less inclined to remote work.

This document is dedicated to the qualitative analysis of organizational processes related to remote and hybrid work, while the quantitative analysis of organizational processes is addressed in a separate document¹, focusing exclusively on a single organization.

2. Qualitative analyses mapping the organisational and the social processes

The SMEs involved in the study adopted different approaches to the introduction of remote work, reflecting a variety of organisational processes. In many SMEs, remote work was introduced without formal collective regulation, often due to the absence of internal trade union representation. This led to more informal management, with individual agreements between employees and managers rather than formal company regulations or collective contracts. In some cases, such as in micro-enterprises, the management of RW remained flexible and dependent on individual decisions, with employees organising their remote work based on their needs and the company's objectives.

Company size significantly influenced the management of RW. Micro-enterprises, for instance, did not perceive the need to formalise remote work, relying instead on trust and informal collaboration among partners and employees. In these organisations, the workflow was maintained through continuous communication between colleagues, often lacking formal hierarchy and rigid division of responsibilities.

In medium-sized SMEs, two trends emerged: some companies adopted a more formal and centralised management style, implementing company regulations on RW to ensure tighter control of work activities, while others maintained a flexible approach, encouraging worker autonomy in managing time and tasks remotely. Differences in RW adoption were also linked to the nature of the work performed. SMEs in manufacturing or those requiring direct customer interaction, such as advertising firms, were more resistant to RW, preferring on-site work to maintain the quality of human relations and ensure greater control.

In contrast, companies in the financial and communication sectors viewed remote work as an opportunity to improve operational efficiency. These companies, already partly digitalised before the pandemic, quickly integrated new tools to enable employees to work remotely, resulting in productivity gains and reduced management costs. Some SMEs adopted a hybrid work model, with

¹ See Deliverable 8 (Transparent processes for smart work in the mountain reality).

employees alternating between on-site and remote workdays, aiming to balance the flexibility of RW with the effectiveness of in-person work.

A key finding from the analysis is the resistance to change from some managerial sectors, particularly in less digitalised companies. The transition to a work model based more on trust than control posed challenges, especially for SMEs that had never considered remote work as a viable solution before the pandemic. In these cases, the digitalisation process played a crucial role in containing resistance and facilitating the transition to agile work.

3. The information flow and the communication flow and the tools most used

Remote work has profoundly transformed communication flows within SMEs, accelerating the adoption of digital tools to facilitate collaboration and coordination among colleagues. Before the pandemic, internal communication in many SMEs relied primarily on phone calls and emails, with limited adoption of digital platforms. The pandemic crisis forced companies to quickly integrate new technologies to maintain business continuity, especially during lockdown periods.

Videoconferencing and online collaboration platforms, such as Microsoft Teams, Zoom, and Google Meet, have become essential tools for managing remote work. These tools enabled companies to organise virtual meetings, facilitate team communication, and coordinate work activities more efficiently. However, the adoption of these tools was faster and more structured in companies with a high level of digitalisation, such as those operating in the ICT or financial sectors, while in traditionally less digitalised SMEs, the transition to online collaboration tools was slower and more challenging.

SMEs that adopted RW more flexibly, especially in the communication and services sectors, made extensive use of corporate chat and collaboration platforms to manage daily tasks. In these companies, the use of chats for quick, informal communications became a common practice, often replacing emails for faster and more operational communications. Videoconferencing, on the other hand, was reserved for weekly or monthly meetings, particularly for strategic decisions or inter-departmental discussions.

Larger companies included in the study demonstrated greater awareness of the opportunities and challenges associated with digital communication. Technological infrastructure played a crucial role in determining the quality of information flow. Companies with a solid digital infrastructure reported improvements in internal communication, thanks to the ability to more effectively monitor remote employees and facilitate problem-solving through collaborative platforms. However, even in these companies, informal communication, which usually occurs spontaneously in on-site work contexts, was limited by remote work, negatively impacting the timely resolution of issues.

Finally, in many of the SMEs interviewed, it was noted that despite progress in adopting digital tools, there remains a preference for in-person meetings when it comes to strategic or important decisions. This reflects a certain cultural resistance to a full transition to digital, highlighting that despite the benefits of remote work, physical presence is still considered essential for certain communicative and decision-making processes.

4. From Organizational Processes Mapping to Organizational Best Practices for SMEs

The COVID-19 pandemic has driven small and medium enterprises (SMEs) to adapt rapidly to remote work (RW) and hybrid work (HW) structures. Unlike larger corporations, which often had established remote work policies and extensive digital infrastructures, SMEs faced unique challenges, adjusting to RW and HW with fewer resources and often limited digital support. Adapting to these new work

models required SMEs to become creative in leveraging their existing resources, seeking new digital solutions, and building flexible policies suited to their unique needs. Based on interviews with SME managers in North-West Italy (Piedmont and Aosta Valley regions in particular), this document outlines best practices for implementing RW and HW effectively, providing SMEs with insights into optimizing communication, fostering trust, maintaining productivity, and ensuring employee well-being.

5. Adapting Remote Work Based on Company Size and Industry Needs

SMEs vary significantly in their approach to RW and HW, and company size and industry requirements are key determinants in shaping these strategies. Several trends and challenges were identified among SMEs, highlighting the importance of adapting remote work based on these cited factors.

Micro-enterprises, which typically have limited resources, often rely heavily on informal, trust-based work models. In these setups, employees are granted the flexibility to organize their RW and HW schedules according to both individual and organizational needs. The flexibility encouraged in micro-enterprises fosters a collaborative work culture where employees have the freedom to balance work and life. However, without formal structures, there is a greater need for transparency and regular updates to avoid misalignment. Communication channels in these firms are frequently informal, relying on group chats or direct messages to convey essential information and updates.

In micro-enterprises, trust is fundamental, yet it also requires periodic check-ins and feedback loops to ensure alignment with broader company objectives. Establishing weekly or bi-weekly team updates helps employees stay in sync, and the use of shared online calendars or basic project tracking tools can provide a centralized platform for task tracking and coordination.

For Medium-sized enterprises, structured policies around RW and HW are common. Implementing formalized policies, often with union agreements or HR guidelines, helps these firms maintain consistency, productivity, and accountability. Structured guidelines also aid in tracking the output and performance of remote and hybrid workers, providing both employees and managers with a clearer understanding of expectations. Medium-sized firms in sectors such as finance, communication, and digital services are well-suited for this approach, as they often benefit from pre-existing digital infrastructure and standardized workflows.

Medium-sized enterprises have the opportunity to incorporate structured training sessions that support employees in developing skills for managing remote and hybrid work effectively. Many firms conduct onboarding sessions dedicated to familiarizing employees with the company's RW and HW policies, which may include specific guidelines on communication tools, reporting, and goal setting. A robust onboarding process strengthens employees' confidence in RW and HW models and clarifies expectations early in their journey with the company.

In client-facing and manufacturing sectors, RW and HW are more challenging to implement due to the need for physical presence to maintain quality control and customer relationships. However, even in these sectors, some roles (such as administrative support or marketing) can adopt RW/HW to provide a more flexible work arrangement for staff. This hybrid structure allows operational continuity without sacrificing the in-person customer experience or quality standards required in these industries.

6. Using Digital Tools to Facilitate Communication and Workflow

Digital tools are critical for maintaining communication, coordination, and workflow in remote and hybrid environments. The right tools can significantly improve productivity, foster collaboration, and prevent information silos that might otherwise form in a remote setting.

Particularly useful are Instant Messaging Platforms: real-time messaging platforms have become invaluable in SMEs that rely on agile decision-making. Platforms enable employees to communicate instantly, replacing slower, more formal email exchanges with a quicker and more spontaneous flow of information. The immediate nature of these tools reduces response times, allows for immediate feedback, and provides a collaborative space where all team members can stay up-to-date. Furthermore, these platforms allow for departmental channels or group chats, creating focused spaces for discussion without overwhelming employees with unrelated updates.

Instant messaging platforms also allow teams to separate channels by topic, project, or department, making it easier for employees to access relevant information without navigating a cluttered inbox. Many SMEs leverage these channels to improve response times and enable transparent, open discussions.

Videoconferencing is an adopted and efficient solution, but some SMEs. However, some managers in small and medium enterprises still experience resistance to adopting it for meetings where strategic decisions are made. In any case, while instant messaging is suitable for quick interactions, videoconferencing is essential for deeper discussions, allowing for face-to-face engagement that enhances communication quality. SMEs using video meetings report improved understanding and alignment on key projects, as well as greater cohesion among remote teams. Establishing meeting agendas and defining participant roles also contributes to more efficient meetings.

Digital task management platforms are used in some SMEs to manage project timelines, assign tasks, and keep track of deliverables. These tools allow employees to visualize project progress, ensuring that deadlines and goals are visible to everyone involved. For SMEs with limited resources, these tools streamline processes, minimizing time lost on miscommunication and allowing managers to easily track task completion and productivity. Project management tools help employees stay organized, making it easier to prioritize work and adjust schedules when needed. For SMEs with minimal digital experience, training sessions on these tools are beneficial, helping employees become familiar with the platforms and encouraging a smooth transition to remote workflows.

7. Investing in Digital Literacy and Cybersecurity

With increased reliance on digital tools, cybersecurity and digital literacy have become essential priorities for SMEs. Unlike large corporations with dedicated IT departments, SMEs may have fewer resources, which makes secure practices and digital skills development especially crucial.

Best practices for digital literacy and security in SMEs include:

- Providing basic digital skills training. Training employees on essential digital tools is invaluable, especially for SMEs that previously relied on in-person workflows. Short training sessions help employees adapt to new platforms, improving productivity and minimizing disruptions. Training sessions bridge knowledge gaps, ensuring that all employees, regardless of their initial digital skill level, can confidently use the necessary tools. Digital literacy encompasses not only learning the technical skills for new platforms but also understanding cybersecurity basics, such as identifying phishing emails or managing sensitive information securely.
- Implementing cybersecurity protocols: as remote work exposes SMEs to cybersecurity risks,

implementing robust protocols is crucial. Basic measures such as VPNs, secure access controls, and data encryption offer a first layer of protection. Additionally, setting up two-factor authentication, encouraging regular password updates, and conducting simulations to spot vulnerabilities are effective ways to protect company information. SMEs may also benefit from using software that monitors and prevents unauthorized access attempts, ensuring that data remains secure.

- Cybersecurity training. SMEs can mitigate potential risks by running regular cybersecurity training for all employees, helping them recognize and respond to potential threats. This reinforces the company's commitment to secure remote operations and prepares employees to act if they encounter suspicious activity.
- Maintaining compliance with data privacy laws. Compliance with data protection regulations is critical for remote SMEs, especially when dealing with personal or financial data. Establishing clear data access and confidentiality guidelines ensures employees follow industry standards. Training employees on compliance policies helps protect sensitive customer information, reducing the risk of data breaches and avoiding potential fines or reputational damage. This is especially important for SMEs in, for example, finance sectors, where data security is highly regulated.

8. Building a Trust-Based Culture and Minimizing Micromanagement

Transitioning to RW and HW requires a shift from traditional, control-based management styles to a trust-based approach that emphasizes accountability and results. In SMEs, this shift is especially critical, as smaller teams and limited resources require managers to empower employees, minimize supervision, and focus on outcomes rather than tasks.

Best practices for fostering a trust-based work culture include:

- Focusing on results, not on time. SMEs benefit from prioritizing goals and project outcomes rather than monitoring employees' hours. By emphasizing deliverables and setting clear deadlines, managers empower employees to work independently, creating a sense of trust and responsibility. Employees who feel trusted to manage their schedules are often more motivated and perform better, ultimately contributing to a positive work environment;
- Regular check-ins and feedback. While micromanagement is discouraged, regular check-ins help maintain a connection between managers and employees. Weekly or biweekly feedback sessions provide an opportunity for managers to stay updated on project progress, address potential challenges, and offer support. Constructive feedback during these sessions helps employees grow, encourages open communication, and ensures alignment on company goals. Feedback is most effective when managers create a supportive space for dialogue. In SMEs, where roles may overlap, establishing clear feedback channels helps employees understand how they contribute to overall business goals.

9. Maintaining Work-Life Balance

One of the biggest challenges associated with RW and HW in SMEs is maintaining a healthy work-life balance. Flexible work structures can sometimes blur the lines between personal and professional time, leading to an increased risk of burnout. SMEs that implement supportive practices for work-life balance report higher employee satisfaction and retention.

Best practices for achieving a balance in SMEs include:

- Encouraging regular breaks: remote and hybrid work can often lead to extended hours and

increased screen time. To mitigate burnout, managers should encourage regular breaks throughout the day, such as short breaks for stretching or longer breaks for lunch. Flexibility in break times allows employees to recharge, sustain focus, and avoid fatigue, ultimately maintaining their productivity and engagement over time;

- Setting clear boundaries for remote hours. Many SMEs have found success by establishing defined “working hours” for remote employees. Setting clear guidelines for work and personal time helps employees disconnect, preventing overwork. These boundaries help maintain employee well-being and ensure that personal time is respected. When employees are expected to set their schedules, establishing “core hours”— blocks of time when all team members are available for meetings or urgent discussions —provides the necessary structure for collaboration without compromising flexibility;
- Limiting remote days for team cohesion. To foster team cohesion, some SMEs adopt hybrid models that limit remote work to specific days. This setup allows for a balance between autonomy and social interaction, helping employees build relationships and stay connected to the company culture. Hybrid schedules also give employees the opportunity to participate in hands-on projects or collaborate on-site, fostering a sense of unity that can be challenging to achieve through RW alone. In SMEs where teamwork is fundamental, scheduling “in-office” days for collaborative projects or quarterly team-building activities can strengthen the bonds between remote and on-site workers.

For SMEs, maintaining a strong sense of community and a supportive work environment is essential to sustaining productivity in hybrid settings.

10. Fostering Employee Engagement and Well-being

Maintaining employee engagement is essential for motivation and satisfaction, particularly in remote or hybrid settings. SMEs that implement engagement strategies report improvements in productivity, morale, and retention, which are fundamental to their success.

Best practices for fostering employee engagement include:

- Promoting regular team-building activities. Virtual team-building events or in-office gatherings encourage connection and camaraderie. These activities build a sense of belonging and support team dynamics, which can be difficult to maintain in a remote setting. SMEs can organize virtual coffee breaks or hybrid team-building retreats to help employees bond and stay engaged;
- Supporting physical and psychological well-being. Offering resources for physical and psychological well-being — such as access to wellness programs and ergonomic guidance — contributes positively to employee morale. For example, providing guidance on setting up ergonomic workstations helps employees avoid strain and discomfort in home settings. Regular well-being initiatives can create a culture that values self-care health, leading to increased job satisfaction. Promoting work-life balance and psychological health support further underscores an SME’s commitment to employee well-being, making employees feel valued and understood;
- Offering flexible work options. Flexibility in schedules, work locations, and even remote days fosters a positive work environment. For SMEs, regularly gathering feedback on RW and HW arrangements allows managers to tailor policies based on evolving needs, thus ensuring that employees feel supported and engaged. Flexibility is often one of the main factors contributing to employee satisfaction and productivity, particularly in smaller firms where team members may take on multiple roles. By offering flexibility, SMEs not only retain talent but also cultivate a dynamic work culture where employees are free to bring their best selves to their work.

11. Conclusion

The adoption of remote and hybrid work models has transformed how SMEs operate, offering both opportunities and challenges. By implementing the outlined best practices, SMEs can maximize the potential benefits of RW and HW, such as enhanced productivity, flexibility, and employee satisfaction. Key factors for success include fostering a trust-based culture, investing in digital literacy and cybersecurity, prioritizing employee well-being, and maintaining clear communication.

In the long term, SMEs that adapt to these new work models build resilience against future disruptions, empowering them to remain agile and competitive. With these strategies, SMEs can create supportive work environments that meet the unique needs of small, agile business structures, ultimately leading to improved organizational performance, employee engagement, and sustainable growth.

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